
ANALYSIS OF DISALLOWANCE OF CESS AS BUSINESS EXPENDITURE AND RETROSPECTIVE PENALTY IMPOSITION

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ABSTRACT

The imposition and collection of taxes have historically been one of the most divisive practices. It has been described by critics as nothing more than sanctioned theft. Its supporters elevate it to the status of a crucial instrument for financing public welfare and realising egalitarianism, an elusive ideal. As with all such disagreements, the truth may lie somewhere in the centre, especially when a tax is applied retroactively. The Finance Act of 2004 was the first to introduce the education cess. The government then discontinued the "education cess" and the "secondary and higher education cess" in the Budget Act of 2018 and instituted a new cess known as the "health and education cess." The tax deductibility of school taxes has generated a great deal of discussion and controversy in the legal world, with arguments and decisions available on both sides of the issue. The Finance Act of 2022's amendments, which seek to "clarify" that cess is not an allowable business expense under Section 40(a)(ii) of the IT Act, is the main subject of this paper. This essay will look at how to read and differentiate between a tax, surcharge, and cess. The second topic this study aims to address is the question of tax statutes' criminal retrospectivity. Examined and questioned as part of the examination are the revisions that regard authorised claims of cess deduction as "under-reporting" income for the purposes of Section 270A of the IT Act.

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I. INTRODUCTION

“The art of taxation consists of so plucking the goose as to obtain the largest amount of feathers with the smallest amount of hissing.”

- *Jean Baptiste Colbert*

One of the most contentious activities in the history has been the levying and collecting of taxes. Critics have characterized it as nothing less than legalized thievery. Its proponents raise it to the level of a significant tool for funding public welfare and achieving the elusive goal of egalitarianism. The truth may lay somewhere in the middle, as it does in all such disputes, particularly when a tax is implemented retrospectively.

Education cess was introduced for the first time by the Finance Act 2004.² Subsequently, under the Budget Act 2018,³ the Government ended 'education cess' and 'secondary and higher education cess' and implemented a new cess, by the name of 'Health and education cess'. There has been significant discussion and debate in the legal community regarding the tax deductibility of education taxes, and there are judgements and reasoning accessible on both sides of the spectrum.

The paper focuses in particular on the revisions that were introduced by the Finance Act of 2022,⁴ that aim to "clarify" that cess is not a permitted business expense under Section 40(a)(ii) of the IT Act.⁵ This paper will examine interpretation and distinguishment between cess, tax and surcharge. The second issue this paper seeks to highlight is the issue of penal retrospectivity of tax statutes. As part of the examination, the modifications that consider approved claims of cess deduction to be "under-reporting" of income for the purposes of Section 270A⁶ of the IT Act are also examined and criticized.

² Finance Act 2004-05.

³ Finance Act 2018-19.

⁴ Finance Act 2022-23.

⁵ Section 40(a)(ii), Income Tax Act, 1961.

⁶ Section 270, Income Tax Act, 1961.

II. THE AMENDMENT INTRODUCED

The Hon. Finance Minister proposed amending Section 40(a)(ii) of the Income Tax Act, 1961,⁷ by inserting an Explanation to the effect that the term "tax" used therein shall also include "any surcharge or cess, by whatever name called, on any income chargeable to tax under the head "Profits and Gains of Business or Profession." The Budget 2022–23 speech provided clarification on the legal position regarding the treatment of cess and surcharge in the computation of income charges.

The Finance Act changed Section 40 of the IT Act by adding an explanation "clarifying" that any surcharge or cess, by whatever name called, on such tax, shall be included and shall be deemed to have always been included for the purposes of Section 40(a)(ii). According to Clause 13 of the Finance Act, the explanation will be considered to have been incorporated into the act with effect from April 1st, 2005.⁸ It should be noted that this adjustment is planned to be implemented retroactively starting on April 1, 2005, which will apply to AY 2005-06 and later years.⁹

The Finance Act also inserts Section 155(18),¹⁰ which specifies that any accepted claims of deduction for cess as a business expense will be considered underreported income for the purposes of Section 270A (3) (which deals with penalty for under-reporting of income)¹¹. The Assessing Officer ("AO") will therefore reevaluate the assessee's total income for that prior year based on this information and make any necessary adjustments. It is important to notice that this section clearly indicates that Section 154's rules—which deal with fixing mistakes—will apply. In addition, the four-year limitation period under Section 154(7) would start on April 1st, 2021, from the conclusion of the preceding year.¹²

While the modification specifically removes the defences provided by Section 270A(6) of the IT Act, it also subjects assesseees to the penalty under Section 270A. Among these defences include the assessee's honest actions, the disclosure of all relevant facts, and others. However, the proviso to the newly added Section 155(18) gives assesseees the choice to voluntarily submit an application

⁷ Section 40(a)(ii), Income Tax Act, 1961.

⁸ Clause 13, Finance Act, 2022.

⁹ Aanchal Magazine, *A new retro amendment: Cess, surcharge are not deduction*, Indian Express, 2 Feb, 2022. (<https://indianexpress.com/article/business/budget/cess-surcharge-are-not-deduction-7752283/>).

¹⁰ Section 155(18), Income Tax Act, 1961.

¹¹ Section 270A(3), Income Tax Act, 1961.

¹² Section 154(7), Income Tax Act, 1961.

to the AO seeking a recalculation of the total income without permitting the deduction of cess as a business expense for the relevant prior year. Such voluntarily compliance wouldn't be considered to fall under Section 270A's definition of income reporting. As a result, no fine would be imposed.¹³

III. BRIEF BACKGROUND AND NEED FOR AMENDMENT

Currently via the Finance Act 2018, regardless of which income tax bracket a person is in, a 4% "Health and Education Cess" is being charged. Moreover, the "Health and Education Cess" is assessed on the total amount of tax and surcharge due, not just the tax due on income derived from company or professional profits and gains.

The amounts that cannot be subtracted from income charged under the heading "Profits and gains of business or profession" are listed in Section 40 of the Act. Sub-clause (ii) of clause (a) of section 40 of the Act provides that any sum paid on account of any rate or tax levied on the profits or gains of any business or profession or assessed at a proportion of, or otherwise on the basis of, any such profits or gains shall not be deducted in computing the income chargeable under the head "Profits and gains of business or profession".

It is important to note at this point that Section 10(4) of the former Act, the Income Tax Act of 1922,¹⁴ clearly called for the disallowance of "cess," in contrast to section 40(a)(ii) of the current Act, the Income Tax Act of 1961. Further, section 115JB of the Income Tax Act, 1961 categorically included 'cess' within the meaning of the term 'income tax'.¹⁵

The word "cess" was categorically included in Section 10(4) of the Income Tax Act, 1922, meaning that it was to be disallowed when calculating income from business or profession, according to a review of the aforementioned sections. Similar to this, it is categorically stated to add back book profits in accordance with section 115JB of the Act. Yet, the Act's section 40(a)(ii) language makes no mention of subtracting "cess" from the taxpayer's profits or gains from their trade or profession. As a result, it has been recommended in the budget to change Section 40(a)(ii)

¹³ CIRCULAR NO. - 23/2022, DATED 3rd NOVEMBER, 2022, by the Finance Ministry.

¹⁴ Section 10(4), Income Tax Act, 1922.

¹⁵ Section 115JB, Income Tax Act, 1961.

of the Act so that "any surcharge or cess, by whatever name called, on such tax" is included in the definition of "tax" in that section.

IV. JURISPRUDENCE ON THE INTERPRETATION OF CESS PRIOR TO THE AMENDMENT

On the contention of deductibility of health and education cess being expenditure and thus deductible, there have been cases on both sides of the spectrum. The Bombay High Court was asked to determine whether paying "cess" was acceptable as a business expense under the IT Act in the case of *Sesa Goa v. JCIT*.¹⁶ Taking a rigorous reading of Section 40(a)(ii) of the IT Act, the HC pointed out that while the clause specifically stipulates that taxes cannot be subtracted from business profits, there is no limitation against deducting expenses that have the characteristics of cesses. A subject cannot be taxed unless he complies with the wording of the law, according to a long-standing principle upheld by the HC.¹⁷

This opinion was supported by the fact that the Income Tax Bill, 1961, which was presented to the Parliament, clearly included "cess, rate, or tax" within its purview. However, the word "cess" was removed from Section 40(a) when the bill was presented to the Select Committee of the Parliament.

The distinction between the terms "cess" and "tax" has always been important, even when we look beyond a rigorous interpretation and at the legislative meaning. In the matter of *Chambal Fertilizers v. CIT*,¹⁸ the Rajasthan High Court came to a similar decision. Some Income Tax Appellate Tribunal ("ITAT") benches started providing assesseees with relief by allowing them to claim cess as a business expense as a result of these two decisions. It is in this context that the Finance Act sought to make an intervention¹⁹

On the other end of the spectrum, there are also decisions in favor of the revenue department. Kolkata branch of the Income-tax Appellate Tribunal's ruling in the case of *Kanoria Chemicals and Industries Ltd.*,²⁰ was directly at odds with earlier ITAT rulings as well as the decisions of the

¹⁶ *Sesa Goa Ltd. v. JCIT* [[2020] 117 taxmann.com 96 (Bombay).

¹⁷ *CIT v. Motors & General Stores*, 1964 SCC ONLINE AP 44.

¹⁸ *Chambal Fertilisers & Chemicals Ltd. v. JCIT* [[2019] 107 taxmann.com 484 (Rajasthan).

¹⁹ *Esakki Ammal K., Skeptic Nature of Education Cess - An Allowable Expenditure or Not?*, 28 *Supremo Amicus* [277] (2022).

²⁰ *M/s. Kanoria Chemicals & Industries Ltd* ITA No. 2184/Kol/2018 (TS-1129- ITAT2021 Kol).

Bombay High Court and Rajasthan High Court mentioned above. The Kolkata ITAT referred to the conflicting decisions and appropriately dismissed them when it made the revenue-supporting decision. Based on the Supreme Court's ruling in the case of CIT v. K Srinivasani,²¹ the ITAT prohibited the education cess expenditure. The Supreme Court adopted the reasoning that, in the Finance Acts' provisions from 2004 and 2011, the "education cess" is a separate surcharge added to income taxes. The Honorable Supreme Court determined in the matter of K. Srinivasan that surcharge and additional surcharge are included in income tax.

As per the memorandum to the Finance Bill 2022, the Circular needs to be read in the context that it does not specifically refer to the 'cess' imposed by the Central Government. Hence, cess and surcharge are a tax levied in the form of surcharge and cess. The memorandum further stated that since the judgments of the Rajasthan High Court and Bombay High Court did not consider the judgment of the Hon'ble Supreme Court in K Srinivasani, the judgments of these two High Courts appear to be per incuriam.

A cess may resemble a tax or a fee, but it is imposed for a particular reason that is specified in the charging legislation.²² A cess is referred to in Article 270 of the Constitution.²³ A tax is an obligatory payment that the government collects from the general population and uses for public purposes²⁴. On the other hand, the government imposes a fee for a certain facility or service that is offered or supplied. A surcharge, on the other hand, is a levy on tax levied for the benefit of the union, in accordance with Article 271 of the Constitution.²⁵

All tax, cess, and surcharge revenue is deposited in the Consolidated Fund of India. The government uses the cess money that has been set aside in the fund for the designated purpose. In contrast to a cess, a surcharge does not require a purpose to be specified at the time of assessment, and the Union is free to use the surcharge profits however it sees proper. If the terms "tax/surcharge" and "cess" were to be used synonymously, there would be no need to earmark cess

²¹ CIT Vs. K. Srinivasan” (1972) 83 ITR 346.

²² Aparna Banerjea, Govt Nullifies retro tax; introduces bill to amend Income Tax Act, Live Mint, Aug 5, 2021. (<https://www.livemint.com/economy/govt-to-amend-income-tax-act-nullify-retro-taxdemands-11628164822039.html>)

²³ Article 270, Constitution of India, 1950.

²⁴ Vol. 1, The law of Income Tax by Kanga and Palkhivala – 8th Edition.

²⁵ Article 271, Constitution of India, 1950.

earnings for a specific purpose, and they would also be included in the dividable pot of money that would be distributed to the states, which is currently not the case.²⁶

The term "cess" is used in the levy's title. Moreover, the element of a cess is revealed in the title, which indicates the purpose. Yet, the Finance Act of 2018's (and the finance acts preceding it) portion imposing the health and education cess uses ambiguous terminology.²⁷ Without realizing that there is a distinction between the two sorts of taxes under the Constitution, the section uses both cess and surcharge in the same line. The government has just described the education cess as an additional surcharge, but it still functions as a cess in substance. An interpretation provided in contravention of the Indian Constitutional distinction between the two levies, cannot be considered genuine. As a result, without clearly identifying and referring to education cess as an extra surcharge under the Finance Act, it must be disregarded in contrast to its true character and structure. Thus, this reasoning calls into question the reasoning adopted by the Supreme Court in *K. Srinivasan* when it held that, the "education cess" is a separate surcharge added to income taxes.

V. OVERTURNING JUDICIAL DECISIONS BY LEGISLATING RETROSPECTIVELY

The legislature's habit of adopting retrospective revisions to reverse judicial rulings in the assessee's favour has been a long-running subject of debate in Indian tax law for many years. The *Vodafone*²⁸ and *Cairn* tax dispute,²⁹ in which the Parliament sought to retroactively tax indirect transfers of assets in order to overturn the Supreme Court's judgement in favour of the assesseees, attracted considerable media attention to the problem. The issue, which lasted more than ten years, was ultimately resolved in the assesseees' favour by an international arbitration panel. The Taxation Laws (Amendment) Act, 2021³⁰ was passed by the Parliament in response to this, with the intention of repealing the retroactive taxes enacted by the Finance Act of 2012.³¹

²⁶ Courts have, on multiple occasions, considered 'cess' as a surcharge itself. See Ashrita Prasad Kotha, Cess or Surcharge: The Distinction is significant for the Taxpayer, EPW Vol. 53, Issue no. 8, 24th Feb, 2018.

²⁷ Finance Act 2018-19,

²⁸ *Vodafone International Holdings BV v. Union of India*, [2012] 17 taxmann.com 202 /204 Taxman 408 (SC).

²⁹ *Cairn Energy PLC and Cairn UK Holdings Limited v. The Republic of India* (PCA Case No. 2016-7).

³⁰ The Taxation Laws (Amendment) Act, 2021.

³¹ Finance Act of 2012.

The administration firmly asserted that it does not intend to impose retroactive taxes and that it wants to establish a clear, equitable, and transparent tax system while endorsing the legislation. However, despite a strong accusation that such retroactive revisions do not hold up under scrutiny on the grounds of fairness and equity, it appears that no lessons have been learned. The Parliament's actions to overturn judicial judgements by retroactively classifying cess deductions as "under-reporting" of income demonstrate little change in their long-standing strategy.³²

VI. PRINCIPLES OF RETROSPECTIVE TAX STATUTES

The judiciary has repeatedly approved retrospective changes to tax laws that are solely declaratory or curative in nature.³³ But, a “substantive” change in the law that retroactively creates a completely new responsibility would be against the letter of the Constitution. In the case of *Union of India v. M/S Martin Lotto Agencies Limited*,³⁴ the Supreme Court made it clear that changes to current rules cannot be introduced without reasonable cause under the guise of clarification. The Constitution's Article 19(1)(g)³⁵ and Article 14³⁶ both state that basic rights are violated when new tax obligations are imposed that are retrospective in character. The law requires that contradictions be cleared up in the public's favor, even when declaratory or curative revisions are involved. The Delhi High Court ruled in *Ansal Housing and Construction Ltd. v. ACIT*,³⁷ that any changes to tax laws must be made with the intention of helping taxpayers, not tax authorities, overcome any challenges. The retrospective amendment's lack of clarity regarding the norms and regulations it imposes could lead to ambiguities in the law, which would make it illegal.³⁸ The High Court of Bombay used the maxim "lex non-cogit ad impossibilia" to establish that a party could not be expected to perform the impossible task of foreseeing the future and complying with a law that would be introduced at a later point in time.³⁹

³²Niranjana A., *The Fallouts of Retrospective Amendments in Taxing Statutes: A Critical Analysis*, 4 INT'L J.L. MGMT. & HUMAN. 1221 (2021).

³³ *Lohia Machines Ltd and Anr vs. Union of India* -(1985) 152 ITR 308 (SC).

³⁴ *Union of India v. M/S Martin Lotto Agencies Limited*, 2007 SCC ONLINE SIKK 3.

³⁵ Article 19(1)(g), Constitution of India, 1950

³⁶ Article 14, Constitution of India, 1950.

³⁷ *Ansal Housing & Construction Ltd. v. ACIT* (2018) 256 Taxman 294 (SC).

³⁸ *Vania Silk Mills (P.) Ltd. v. CIT*, [1991] 59 Taxman 3/191 ITR 647 (SC).

³⁹ *Commr. of Income Tax v. NGC Networks India Pvt. Limited*, 2018 SCC ONLINE BOM 4427.

VII. CLARIFACTORY OR SUBSTANTIVE AMENDMENT

It is a well-established legal notion that taxes may be levied retroactively by enacting substantive amendments. Although there are criteria to evaluate whether an amendment would function retroactively (i.e., is the amendment "clarificatory" or "substantive"), the same is only used where the amendment is ambiguous or imprecise about whether it applies retroactively or not. The Parliament clearly intended to give the amendment retroactive effect when it said that the explanation to Section 40(a)(ii) shall be understood to have been inserted with effect from April 1st, 2005. Hence, the fact that the amendment takes effect retroactively cannot be used as a basis for any constitutional challenge. When the legislative aim is easily obvious, it is not required to determine whether the change is substantive or clarificatory, but such an exercise is crucial in this case.⁴⁰

It is pretty obvious that the explanation included is a substantive alteration, regardless of the terminology in the amendment. Clarifying the law and correcting a provision that has a clear defect or infirmity is the only goal of a clarificatory amendment. But, there was no such flaw or ambiguity in Section 40(a)(ii). In *Sesa Goa*,⁴¹ the Bombay High Court correctly concluded that cess and tax are two entirely different ideas. It is evident that the legislature intended to regard these two terms differently, at least for the purposes of Section 40(a), given that the word cess was expressly excluded from the IT Act while existing in the Income Tax Bill, 1961.

Therefore, the language of Section 40(a)(ii) was crystal plain and did not provide room for interpretation or opposing views. The substantive tax liability of the assessee is directly impacted by the determination that cess is tax. Therefore, the amendment must be considered a substantive one regardless of the nomenclature.

It would have still constituted a valid amendment if the legislature had specifically added "cess" to the main clause of Section 40(a)(ii), as long as they made it clear that the substantive change would take effect retrospectively. But, the addition of a "Explanation" to create a substantive change does give rise to a constitutional validity argument against the clause. There are two settled principles in this regard.

⁴⁰ Niranjana A., *The Fallouts of Retrospective Amendments in Taxing Statutes: A Critical Analysis*, 4 INT'L J.L. MGMT. & HUMAN. 1221 (2021).

⁴¹ *Sesa Goa Ltd. v. JCIT* [[2020] 117 taxmann.com 96 (Bombay).

First and foremost, the purpose of an explanation is simply to make the law clearer when there is confusion so that it is compatible with the main goal of the legislation. In the case of *S. Sundaram Pillai vs. V.R. Pattabiraman*,⁴² the Supreme Court also found that an explanation could not alter or modify the enactment in any way. Also, it cannot remove a statutory right that a person has been granted by a legislation.

Second, even while the legislature typically has the power to enact retroactive legislation, such a process cannot be used to merely overturn a court ruling. In the case of *D. Cawasji and Co. vs. State of Mysore*,⁴³ the SC remarked that the retrospective tax modification in question had just one goal: to nullify the consequences of a legally binding decision. Yet, the revision did not make any attempts to fix the flaw or gap in the original clause. In light of this, the SC determined that the vice of Revenue's illegal tax collection remained to taint the levy in the absence of the eradication of the illegality/lacuna that caused the earlier invalidation of assessments.⁴⁴

The Bombay HC in *Sesa Goa*⁴⁵ drew attention to a discrepancy between the terms "cess" and "tax" in the current debate over the disallowance of cess as a business expense. As the word cess does not exist in Section 40(a)(ii), it is permissible to deduct it. The Parliament should have changed the text of Section 40(a)(ii) to clearly include the term cess within the main provision in order to fill this gap. As previously indicated, as long as the legislature specifically granted it retrospective effect, this would be constitutionally acceptable.

The Parliament's strategy is to invent a convincing fiction in the explanation rather than directly addressing the gap. Under the guise of a "clarification," all of this is accomplished. The sheer act of using a deeming fiction reveals that the Parliament views cess and tax to be separate concepts, and that cess would be considered as tax only under a 'legal fiction'. The logical implication of this is that cess is not, in fact, and in actuality, included in the term "tax" as it is used in Section 40(a)(ii). The Explanation goes beyond the terms of Section 40(a)(ii) by effectively adding new words by presuming it to include cess. The Explanation also eliminates a previously existent legal right to

⁴² *S. Sundaram Pillai vs. V.R. Pattabiraman*, 1985 SCC 1 591.

⁴³ *D. Cawasji and Co. vs. State of Mysore*, 1985 SCC 0 63.

⁴⁴ Sudeep Das & Aswath Pai, Can taxpayers claim health and education cess as an allowable expenditure- budget 2022 proposes retrospective disallowance, 18 feb, 2022 (<https://www.taxmann.com/research/direct-tax-laws/top-story/10501000000021390/can-taxpayers-claim-health-education-cess-as-an-allowable-expenditure-%E2%80%93-budget-2022-proposes-retrospective-disallowance-experts-opinion>)

⁴⁵ *Sesa Goa Ltd. v. JCIT* [[2020] 117 taxmann.com 96 (Bombay).

claim a cess deduction as a business expense under the IT Act. The addition of the explanation conflicts with the Supreme Court's ruling in Sundaram Pillai. The Bombay HC's concern about the Section 40(a)(ii) lacuna is not addressed by the introduction of such an Explanation without changing the main clause of the section. As a result, the modification also violates the SC ruling in D. Cawasji.⁴⁶

Therefore, the explanation to Section 40 is potentially invalid not only because it violates the directive of Section 40(a)(ii) and eliminates statutory rights, but also because it is a substantive retrospective amendment that has the express purpose of overturning a court decision without addressing the gap noted therein.

VIII. RETROSPECTIVE PENALTIES

The amendment introduces civil penalties retrospectively by deeming the deducted cess expenditure as under-reported income. Thus, it raises the question about whether a tax statute can impose penalties retrospectively. In the case of Shiv Dutt Rai Fateh Chand v. Union of India,⁴⁷ a division bench of the SC ruled that "civil penalties" are not considered "penalties" under Article 20.⁴⁸ Instead, the Article 20 penalty must be viewed in the specific context of payments relating to liberty. Hence, it is legal to impose a punishment in the past.

At the same time, a three-judge SC panel invalidated a retroactive punishment in the shape of interest in the case of Star India v. Union of India.⁴⁹ The decision in Star India, however, is a relatively short one and does not consider Article 20 arguments or engage with Shiv Dutt Rai.

Although the constitutionality of retrospective penalties is up for debate, the government has circumvented any potential issues by creating present-day liability.⁵⁰ It is clear from reading the modifications that Section 270A only applies if the assessee does not voluntarily file for re-computation of his income and pay the differential tax now. As a result, problems with retroactive penalties have been eliminated in one sense.

⁴⁶ Section 40(a)(ii), Income Tax Act, 1961.

⁴⁷ Shiv Dutt Rai Fateh Chand v. Union of India, 1983 SCC 3 529.

⁴⁸ Article 20, Constitution of India, 1950.

⁴⁹ Star India v. Union of India, 2011 SCC ONLINE DEL 3599.

⁵⁰ Section 270A, Income Tax Act, 1961.

This is a clever way to get around any potential constitutional issues. Nonetheless, this clause is incredibly unfair and effectively coerces the assessee into paying the differential tax as quickly as feasible. To avoid being penalized under Section 270A, assesseees who wish to contest the amendment may want to submit an application under the recently added Section 155(18)⁵¹ and pay the differential tax in protest.

IX. UNSETTLING SETTLED CASES

Remedial orders can only be issued where there is a "mistake apparent on record," as Section 154 of the IT Act makes clear.⁵² Such a mistake must be clear and not something that requires a drawn-out process of analysis and interpretation. The rule is based on the fundamental idea that the assessee or Revenue shouldn't suffer as a result of errors that could occur in orders. Indeed, human error is common. Yet the AO is not permitted to re-examine the situation on its merits and recalculate income under the guise of rectifying orders.

The SC has stated unequivocally that a later court ruling is not a reason to rectify, review, reevaluate, or reopen cases that have already been resolved.⁵³ Even the assessee cannot attempt to reopen cases that have already concluded by pointing to later affirmative rulings.⁵⁴

The newly added Section 155(18)⁵⁵ particularly grants the AO the authority to recompute the assesseees' income in order to circumvent these court roadblocks. In particular, the change gives the AO the power to issue orders under Section 154 that "recompute" the income by disallowing cess expenditure. This goes against Section 154's purpose, which was to fix glaring or patent errors in the assessment order. Even though explicitly giving the AO such authority may not be unlawful, it shows a complete contempt for legal precedents that have emphasized the sanctity that must be granted to settled legal proceedings.

The fact that the limitation period under Section 154(7), which is four years from the date of the previous year, would now start on April 1st, 2021, further demonstrates the provision's draconian nature. So, even with regard to AY 2005–06, the AO may issue rectification orders that disallow

⁵¹ Section 155(18), Income Tax Act, 1961.

⁵² Section 154, Income Tax Act, 1961.

⁵³ DCIT vs. Simplex Concrete Piles (India) Ltd., (2013) 11 SCC 373.

⁵⁴ Mafatlal Industries vs. Union of India, (1997) 5 SCC 536.

⁵⁵ Section 155(18), Income Tax Act, 1961.

the deduction of cess as a business expense. Even though it has been more than 16 years, this disallowance is still possible. Such a manifestly unjust and arbitrary extension of the statute of limitations is unacceptable.

X. TEST OF MANIFEST ARBITRARINESS UNDER ARTICLE 14

The doctrine of manifest arbitrariness, which was reinforced as a part of positive law, by the Supreme Court in *Shayara Bano v. Union of India*,⁵⁶ was also applied by R.F. Nariman J., albeit recently, while dealing with a matter concerning third proviso to Section 254(2)⁵⁷ of the Income tax Act, in *Dy. CIT v. Pepsi Foods Ltd.*⁵⁸ The Supreme Court, in this case discussed the history of successful challenges, levelled against tax statutes, on the touchstone of Article 14 of the Constitution of India.⁵⁹ The Court held the provision disputed to be "manifestly arbitrary being a provision which is capricious, irrational and disproportionate so far as the assessee is concerned".⁶⁰

Numerous aspects of this amendment can be constituted to be manifestly arbitrary under Article 14. Firstly, defences available under section 270A (6) being taken away constitute arbitrariness. Secondly, the retrospective application of the amendment with penal consequences even when the assessor's conduct was bona fide constitutes arbitrariness violating Article 14. Thirdly, the absolute extension of the limitation period such that disallowance can be done despite more than 16 years having passed since is blatantly unfair and arbitrary. It remains to be seen whether such an extension of limitation can pass the test of Manifest Arbitrariness under Article 14 of the Indian Constitution.⁶¹ The question of whether these are or not remains to be decided.

⁵⁶ *Shayara Bano v. Union of India*, 2017 SCC ONLINE SC 963.

⁵⁷ Section 254(2), Income Tax Act, 1961.

⁵⁸ *Dy. CIT v. Pepsi Foods Ltd.*, [2021] 126 taxmann.com 69 (SC).

⁵⁹ *Suraj Mall Mohta & Co. v. A.V. Visvanatha Sastri*, [1955] 1 SCR 448.

⁶⁰ Karan Kumar Khetani, *Invoking Doctrine of Manifest Arbitrariness and Positive Obligation in The Field of Taxation*, 24Aug 2021, (<https://www.taxmann.com/research/direct-tax-laws/top-story/10501000000020834/invoking-doctrine-of-manifest-arbitrariness-and-positive-obligation-in-the-field-of-taxation.aspx>)

⁶¹ Article 14, Constitution of India, 1950.

XI. CONCLUSION

In light of the above, one can conclude that the education cess levied on income tax cannot be disallowed under section 40(a)(ii) and should be allowed as a deduction while computing Income under the head Business or Profession on the basis of the recent judicial decisions.

The principles for fair taxation are now well agreed upon by economists and jurists. Equity and justice, clarity, tax neutrality, economic growth and efficiency, transparency and visibility are among the generally acknowledged rules. The government's approach to tax laws runs directly against the principles of rule of law. Uncertainty has increased as a result of the statute's lack of clarity and consistency and the department's attitude to it and the same has led to worry for the taxpaying public. Retrospective changes only serve to erode taxpayers' faith in the tax system in such circumstances, with the rule of law ultimately suffering as a result. Leaving aside concerns about the constitutionality of the legislation, the tax administration must carefully examine how it changes and enforces the country's tax laws.

